

TWO MORE SOLUTIONS OF NON-COLLINEAR LIBRATION POINTS IN A PLANAR RESTRICTED THREE-BODY PROBLEM WHEN LESS MASSIVE PRIMARY IS AN OBLATE SPHEROID

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Abstract

In this paper the stability of non-collinear libration points in circular restricted three-body problem has been analyzed considering less massive primary as an oblate spheroid. We have considered two cases to find out the location and stability of non-collinear libration points. In case I, it is observed that there exist infinite numbers of non-collinear libration points on the unit circle centered at oblate body and out of these libration points only those lying in the interval $57^\circ \leq \psi \leq 60^\circ$ are stable for different values of critical mass parameter μ_c , where ψ is the angle between m_3 , m_2 and m_1 in the same plane. In case II, the non-collinear libration points exist only in the interval $0^\circ \leq \varphi \leq 140^\circ$ are stable for different values of critical mass parameter μ_c , during the analysis we got a collinear libration point which is stable for $\mu_c \leq 0.127284\dots$

Key Words: Celestial Mechanics, Restricted three-body problem, Libration points, Linear stability.

1. INTRODUCTION

The restricted problem of three bodies is a well known problem. The two masses m_1 and m_2 called primaries are moving around their common center of mass in circular orbits and an infinitesimal mass m_3 is moving in the plane formed by m_1 and m_2 under the Newtonian gravitational attraction of the primaries. To discuss the motion of m_3 is called restricted three-body problem. In the classical case (Szebehely, 1967), there exist three collinear and two non-collinear libration points. The non-collinear libration points form an equilateral triangle with the primaries and stable for a critical value of mass parameter μ_c such that $\mu < \mu_c = 0.0385208965\dots$ while the collinear libration points are unstable for all values of μ .

Recently the restricted three-body problem is studied by many mathematicians, physicists and astronomers. Narayan and Kumar (2011) have studied the effects of the oblateness and the photogravitational of the bigger primary and the oblateness of the smaller primary on the location of the triangular Lagrangian equilibrium points in the elliptical restricted three-body problem. They observed that the range of stability decreases as the oblateness and the radiation pressure parameter increases.

Douskos (2011) has discussed the existence, location and stability of the equilibrium points of the coplanar restricted three-body problem with equal prolate and radiating primaries. He has observed that due to the radiation and negative oblateness parameters, two or four additional collinear equilibrium points exist, in addition to the three Eulerian points of the classical case, making up a total of up to seven collinear points. Four of these additional points, as well as the classical central equilibrium point located at the origin, are stable for certain ranges of the

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parameters. Also, depending on the values of the parameters, up to six additional non-collinear equilibrium points exist, in addition to the triangular Lagrangian points of the classical case. Two of these additional points are located symmetrically above and below the origin and are stable, while the other four are located symmetrically in the four quadrants and are unstable.

Zhang et.al. (2012) have investigated the triangular libration points in the photogravitational restricted three-body problem of variable mass, in which both the attracting bodies are radiating as well and the infinitesimal body vary its mass with time according to Jeans' law. Firstly, they applied the space-time transformation of Meshcherskii in the special case when $q=1/2$, $k=0$, $n=1$, the differential equations of motion of the problem were obtained. Secondly, in analogy to corresponding problem with constant mass, the positions of analogous triangular libration points were obtained, and the fact that these triangular libration points cease to be classical ones when $\alpha \neq 0$, but turn to classical L_4 and L_5 naturally when $\alpha=0$ is pointed out. Lastly, introducing the space-time inverse transformation of Meshcherskii, the linear stability of triangular libration points is tested when $\alpha > 0$. It is seen that the motion around the triangular libration points become unstable in general when the problem with constant mass evolves into the problem with decreasing mass.

Idrisi and Taqvi (2013) have studied a problem in the restricted three body problem in which the smaller primary is an ellipsoid and the bigger is point mass. This paper deals with the existence and the stability of the libration points in the restricted three-body problem when the smaller primary is an ellipsoid. They have determined the equations of motion of the infinitesimal mass which involves elliptic integrals and then investigated the collinear and non collinear libration points and their stability. They have also proved in their work that there exist five collinear libration points L_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$) and the non-collinear libration points lie on the arc of the unit circle centered at the bigger primary and both the collinear and non-collinear libration points are unstable for $0 < \mu \leq 1/2$ and $0 \leq \varphi \leq \pi/2$.

Reena Kumari et. al. (2014) have extended the basic model of the restricted four-body problem introducing two bigger dominant primaries m_1 and m_2 as oblate spheroids when masses of the two primary bodies (m_2 and m_3) are equal. The aim of this study is to investigate the use of zero velocity surfaces and the Poincaré surfaces of section to determine the possible allowed boundary regions and the stability orbit of the equilibrium points. According to different values of Jacobi constant C , we can determine boundary region where the particle can move in possible permitted zones. The stability regions of the equilibrium points expanded due to presence of oblateness coefficient and various values of C , whereas for certain range of t ($100 \leq t \leq 200$), orbits form a shape of cote's spiral. For different values of oblateness parameters A_1 ($0 < A_1 < 1$) and A_2 ($0 < A_2 < 1$), they obtained two collinear and six non-collinear equilibrium points. The non-collinear equilibrium points are stable when the mass parameter μ lies in the interval (0.0190637, 0.647603). However, basins of attraction are constructed with the help of Newton Raphson method to demonstrate the convergence as well as divergence region of the equilibrium points. The nature of basins of attraction of the equilibrium points are less affected in presence and absence of oblateness coefficients A_1 and A_2 respectively in the proposed model.

Singh et. al. (2014) have investigated the motion of a test particle in the vicinity of a binary made of a triaxial primary and a spherical companion moving along elliptic orbits about their common barycenter in the neighborhood of collinear libration points. Their positions and stability are found to be affected by the triaxiality of the bigger primary, and by the semi-major axis and the eccentricity of the binary's orbits as well. The analytic results obtained are applied to binary neutron stars consisting of a bigger triaxial primary and a spherical companion. A numerical analysis shows that the positions of the collinear points of PSR J1518+4904, PSR B1534+12, PSR B1914+16, and PSR B2127+11c are affected by the triaxiality of the bigger primary, and by the eccentricity of the orbits. The stability behavior however remains unchanged: the collinear points remain unstable in the Lyapunov sense.

Idrisi and Taqvi (2014) have investigated the location and stability of the non-collinear libration points when both the primaries are ellipsoids and found that the non-collinear libration points exist only in the interval $52^\circ < \varphi < 90^\circ$ and form an isosceles triangle with the primaries. Further they observed that the non collinear libration points are unstable in $52^\circ < \varphi < 90^\circ$.

Abd El-Salam (2015) has treated the elliptic restricted three-body problem (in brief ERTBP) with oblate and triaxial primaries using the pulsating coordinates. He has derived the mean motion of the system and the locations of the triangular equilibrium points under the considered model. He has also obtained new expressions for these locations as power series in the mass ratio parameter. He has discussed the linear stability of the triangular points and found that the stability regions depend on the eccentricity of the orbits, oblateness coefficient and the triaxial parameters of the primaries. He has observed that when $e=0.25$ the stability region is destroyed completely for the Earth-Moon like system.

Alvarez-Ramírez et.al. (2015) considered the problem of the stability of equilibrium points in the restricted equilateral four-body problem where a particle of negligible mass is moving under the Newtonian gravitational attraction of three positive masses (called *primaries*) which move on circular orbits around their center of masses, such that their configuration is always an equilateral triangle (Lagrangian configuration). They considered the case of two bodies of equal mass, which in a dimensional unit is the parameter of the problem. They investigated the Birkhoff normal form around the linearly stable equilibrium points L_3 for $\mu \in (0, 0.0027096302)$ and, L_5 and L_6 for $\mu \in (0, 0.018858526)$. The quadratic part of the normalized Hamiltonian has no definite sign, so they examine a function which depends on the coefficients of the fourth order normal form and the stability follows from KAM theory if this function is not zero, otherwise the normal form has to be taken to sixth order or higher. This is the case for L_5 and L_6 for one value of μ . They have calculated the sixth order normal form and establish the stability of the points in this case of the failure of the fourth order analysis. They have also discussed the stability at the 2:1 resonances for the equilibrium point L_3 and the symmetrical L_5 and L_6 points.

The aim of this paper is to find out the non-collinear solution of restricted three-body problem under oblate primary model using different approaches. The paper consists of six sections. In section 2, the equations of motion are derived using the potential of oblate spheroid given by MacMillan in 1958 in terms of largest root of the confocal ellipsoids. In section 3, the mean-motion of the primaries as a power series in oblateness factor A is obtained. In section 4, the solution of non-collinear libration points has given in three different approaches. The stability of the non-collinear libration points is discussed in section 5 and results obtained are discussed in the last section.

2. Equations of motion

Let m_2 be an oblate spheroid whose axes are a , b and c ($a = b > c$) and m_1 a point mass ($m_1 > m_2$), are moving in the circular orbits around their center of mass O . An infinitesimal mass m_3 is moving in the plane of motion of m_1 and m_2 . The distances of m_3 from m_1 , m_2 and O are r_1 , r_2 and r respectively. The principal axes of spheroid remains parallel to the synodic axes $Oxyz$ throughout the motion and the equatorial plane of m_2 is coincide with the plane of motion of m_1 and m_2 . Let the line joining m_1 and m_2 be taken as X -axis and O their center of mass as origin. Let the line passing through O and perpendicular to OX and lying in the plane of motion m_1 and m_2 be the Y -axis. Let us consider a synodic system of co-ordinates $Oxyz$ initially coincide with the inertial system $OXYZ$, rotating with angular velocity ω about Z -axis (the z -axis is coincide with Z -axis) (Fig. 1). We wish to find the equations of motion of m_3 using the terminology of Szebehely (1967) in the synodic co-ordinate system and dimensionless variables *i.e.* the distance between the primaries is unity, the unit of time t is such that the gravitational constant $G = 1$ and the sum of the masses of the primaries is unity *i.e.* $m_1 + m_2 = 1$.

Fig. 1: The Configuration of the RTBP when m_2 is an oblate spheroid

Let a, b, c be the semi-axes of the given oblate spheroid such that $a = b > c$ and x, y, z the co-ordinates of the external point P . Let a', b', c' be the semi-axes of the confocal oblate spheroid which passes through P .

Let the equation of the oblate spheroid be

$$\frac{x^2 + y^2}{a^2} + \frac{z^2}{c^2} = 1, \tag{1}$$

The equation of the confocal oblate spheroid whose semi-axes are a', b' and c' such that $a' = b' > c'$ which passes through the point $P(x, y, z)$ is

$$\frac{x^2 + y^2}{a'^2} + \frac{z^2}{c'^2} = 1 \tag{2}$$

Since the oblate spheroids are confocal, we have $a'^2 = a^2 + \kappa$, $b'^2 = b^2 + \kappa$ and $c'^2 = c^2 + \kappa$. Therefore, the Equation

(2) becomes (MacMillan, 1958),

$$\frac{x^2 + y^2}{a^2 + \kappa} + \frac{z^2}{c^2 + \kappa} = 1 \tag{3} \quad \text{The}$$

Equation (3) is a second degree equation in κ . On solving the Equation (3) and neglecting the higher powers of a and c , we get

$$\kappa = x^2 + y^2 + z^2 - a^2 = r^2 - a^2. \tag{4}$$

where r is the distance between the center of mass of oblate spheroid and $P(x, y, z)$.

The potential of the oblate spheroid with axes a and c and density σ at an external point $P(x, y, z)$ is given by (MacMillan, 1958),

$$V = \frac{2\pi\sigma a^2 c}{\sqrt{a^2 - c^2}} \left(1 - \frac{x^2 + y^2 - 2z^2}{2(a^2 - c^2)} \right) \sin^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{a^2 - c^2}{a^2 + \kappa}} + \frac{\pi\sigma a^2 c \sqrt{c^2 + \kappa}}{a^2 - c^2} \frac{x^2 + y^2}{a^2 + \kappa} - \frac{\pi\sigma a^2 c}{a^2 - c^2} \frac{2z^2}{\sqrt{c^2 + \kappa}}, \quad (5)$$

where κ is defined in the equation (4).

The potential of the oblate spheroid m_2 at $P(x, y)$ in our case is therefore given by,

$$-V = \frac{3m_2}{4} \left[\frac{2}{\sqrt{a^2 - c^2}} \left(1 - \frac{(x - x_2)^2 + y^2}{2(a^2 - c^2)} \right) \sin^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{a^2 - c^2}{a^2 + \kappa}} + \frac{\sqrt{c^2 + \kappa}}{a^2 - c^2} \frac{(x - x_2)^2 + y^2}{a^2 + \kappa} \right], \quad (6)$$

where

a, c = semi axes of the oblate spheroid m_2 ,

$$m_2 = \frac{4}{3} \pi a^2 c \sigma = \text{Mass of the oblate spheroid,}$$

$$\kappa = r_2^2 - a^2,$$

$$r_2 = \sqrt{(x - x_2)^2 + y^2}.$$

The equations of the motion of m_3 in the synodic co-ordinate system and dimensionless variables are given by:

$$\ddot{x} - 2n\dot{y} = n^2 x - \frac{1 - \mu}{r_1^3} (x - \mu) - \frac{3\mu(x + 1 - \mu)}{2} \left[\frac{\sqrt{c^2 + \kappa}}{(a^2 + \kappa)(a^2 - c^2)} - \frac{1}{(a^2 - c^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \sin^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{a^2 - c^2}{a^2 + \kappa}} \right], \quad (7)$$

and

$$\ddot{y} + 2n\dot{x} = n^2 y - \frac{1 - \mu}{r_1^3} y - \frac{3\mu}{2} y \left[\frac{\sqrt{c^2 + \kappa}}{(a^2 + \kappa)(a^2 - c^2)} - \frac{1}{(a^2 - c^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \sin^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{a^2 - c^2}{a^2 + \kappa}} \right]. \quad (8)$$

where n is the mean-motion of the primaries.

a, c = semi axes of the oblate spheroid m_2 ,

$$\mu = \frac{m_2}{m_1 + m_2},$$

$$1 - \mu = \frac{m_1}{m_1 + m_2},$$

$$\kappa = r_2^2 - a^2 - c^2,$$

$$r_1^2 = (x - \mu)^2 + y^2,$$

$$r_2^2 = (x + 1 - \mu)^2 + y^2.$$

Now, we define a function Ω such that

$$\Omega = \frac{n^2}{2}(x^2 + y^2) + \frac{1 - \mu}{r_1} + V \quad (9)$$

where V is defined in the Equation (6).

Hence, the Equations (7) and (8) become

$$\ddot{x} - 2n\dot{y} = \Omega_x, \quad (10)$$

$$\ddot{y} + 2n\dot{x} = \Omega_y, \quad (11)$$

where Ω_x and Ω_y are the partial derivatives of Ω with respect to x and y respectively.

The integral analogous to Jacobi integral is

$$(\dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2) = 2\Omega - C. \quad (12)$$

3. Calculation of the mean-motion n of the primaries

Since the primaries m_1 and m_2 are moving in the circular orbits around their center of mass O . Therefore, the mean-motion n of the primaries is given by,

$$n^2 = \frac{F}{m_1 m_2} \quad (13)$$

where F is the gravitational force acting on m_1 due to m_2 .

At m_1 the value of the largest root κ is,

$$\kappa = 1 - a^2. \quad (14)$$

Therefore, at $m_1(x_1, 0)$

$$F = -\frac{\partial V}{\partial x} = \frac{-3m_1 m_2}{2} \left[\frac{\sqrt{c^2 + 1 - a^2}}{(a^2 - c^2)} - \frac{1}{(a^2 - c^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \sin^{-1} \sqrt{a^2 - c^2} \right], \quad (15)$$

Thus, the mean-motion n of the primaries is

$$n^2 = \frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{\sin^{-1} \sqrt{a^2 - c^2}}{(a^2 - c^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} - \frac{\sqrt{c^2 + 1 - a^2}}{(a^2 - c^2)} \right],$$

Let $a^2 - c^2 = A$, therefore

$$n^2 = 1 + \frac{3}{10} A + \frac{9}{56} A^2 + \frac{5}{48} A^3 + \frac{105}{1408} A^4 + \dots \quad (16)$$

If $A = 0$ i.e. m_2 a point mass or spherical in shape then $n = 1$ which is the classical case of the restricted three-body problem (Szebehely, 1967). If we neglect the second and higher powers of A the results are in conformity with those of Bhatnagar and Hallan (1979).

4. Libration Points

The libration points are the singularities of the manifold

$$F(x, y, \dot{x}, \dot{y}) \equiv \dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2 - 2\Omega + C = 0$$

and these points are given by the Equations

$$F_{\dot{x}} = F_{\dot{y}} = F_x = F_y = 0$$

$$i.e. \quad \dot{x} = 0, \dot{y} = 0, \Omega_x = 0, \Omega_y = 0.$$

where

$$\Omega_x = n^2 x - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} (x-\mu) - \frac{3\mu(x+1-\mu)}{2} \left[\frac{\sqrt{c^2 + \kappa}}{(a^2 + \kappa)(a^2 - c^2)} - \frac{1}{(a^2 - c^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \sin^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{a^2 - c^2}{a^2 + \kappa}} \right] = 0,$$

$$\Omega_y = y \left[n^2 - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} - \frac{3\mu}{2} \left(\frac{\sqrt{c^2 + \kappa}}{(a^2 + \kappa)(a^2 - c^2)} - \frac{1}{(a^2 - c^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \sin^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{a^2 - c^2}{a^2 + \kappa}} \right) \right] = 0.$$

Since, $A \ll 1$, therefore considering only linear terms of A , the above equations can be written as

$$\Omega_x = n^2 x - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} (x-\mu) - \frac{\mu(x+1-\mu)}{r_2^3} \left(1 + \frac{3}{10} \frac{A}{r_2^2} \right) = 0, \quad (17)$$

$$\Omega_y = y \left[n^2 - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} - \frac{\mu}{r_2^3} \left(1 + \frac{3}{10} \frac{A}{r_2^2} \right) \right] = 0. \quad (18)$$

The non-collinear libration points are the solution of the equations $\Omega_x = 0$ and $\Omega_y = 0, y \neq 0$ i.e.

$$n^2 x - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} (x-\mu) - \frac{\mu(x+1-\mu)}{r_2^3} \left(1 + \frac{3}{10} \frac{A}{r_2^2}\right) = 0, \quad (19)$$

$$n^2 - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} - \frac{\mu}{r_2^3} \left(1 + \frac{3}{10} \frac{A}{r_2^2}\right) = 0. \quad (20)$$

The Equations (19) and (20) can be solved in following three ways:

Case I: On eliminating r_1 from the Equations (19) and (20), we get

$$n^2 - \frac{1}{r_2^3} \left(1 + \frac{3}{10} \frac{A}{r_2^2}\right) = 0. \quad (21)$$

Since $r_2 = 1$ satisfies the Equation (21) *i.e.* the non-collinear libration points lying on a unit circle centered at the smaller primary m_2 (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Non-collinear Libration Points for $r_2 = 1$

From the Fig. 2, it is seen that $m_2 m_1 = m_2 m_3 = 1$ *i.e.* the non-collinear libration points are forming an isosceles triangle. Let us suppose that the $\psi = \text{angle}(m_1 m_2 m_3)$, $0^\circ \leq \psi, \leq 360^\circ$, therefore the location of the non-collinear libration point $L_4(x, y)$ is given by

$$x = \mu - 1 + \cos\psi, \text{ and } y = \sin\psi, \quad (22)$$

Equation (22) gives the location of all non-collinear libration points lying on the unit circle centered at m_2 for all values of ψ from 0 to 360° except at $\psi = 0^\circ, 180^\circ$ and 360° because for these three values the libration points obtained will be collinear and we are interested only in the non-collinear libration points, so $\psi = 0^\circ, 180^\circ$ and 360° will be neglected.

For $\psi = 60^\circ$, $x = \mu - 1/2$ and $y = \sqrt{3}/2$ which is the classical case of restricted three-body problem.

Case II: On eliminating r_2 from the Equations (19) and (20), we have $r_1 = 1 - \frac{A}{5}$ i.e. the non-collinear

libration points lying on a circle of radius $1 - \frac{A}{5}$, centered at the bigger primary m_1 (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Non-collinear Libration Points for $r_1 = 1 - A / 5$

Let us suppose that $\varphi = \text{angle}(Pm_1m_3)$, $0^\circ \leq \varphi \leq 360^\circ$, therefore the location of the non-collinear libration point L_4 (x, y) is given by

$$x = \mu + p \cos \varphi, \quad y = p \sin \varphi, \quad p = 1 - \frac{A}{5}. \quad (23)$$

Since, $r_2^2 = (x + 1 - \mu)^2 + y^2$, using Eqns. (23) we have $r_2 = \sqrt{1 + 2p \cos \varphi + p^2}$, for different values φ , r_2 can be calculated.

Case III: Using Equation (20) in Equation (19), we have

$$\frac{1}{r_1^3} - \frac{1}{r_2^3} \left(1 + \frac{3A}{10r_2^2} \right) = 0$$

Let $r_2 = 1$, therefore $r_1 = 1 - A / 10$. On solving these two equations we then get

$$x = \mu - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{A}{10}, \quad y = \pm \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \left(1 - \frac{A}{15} \right). \quad (24)$$

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Equations (24) are well known solutions of restricted three-body problem under oblate primary but the above two solutions (22) and (23) are new in the sense that these solutions are not used in the previous studies. So, we include two more solutions in the restricted three-body problem under oblate primary and we will discuss the stability of only these two solutions in the next section.

5. Stability of the Libration Points

The equations of the motion of the infinitesimal mass are

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{x} - 2n\dot{y} &= \Omega_x, \\ \ddot{y} + 2n\dot{x} &= \Omega_y. \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

To study the possible motion of the infinitesimal mass around the libration points let the coordinates of these points are (x_0, y_0) . If we give small displacement (α, β) to (x_0, y_0) , the variation α and β can be written as: $\alpha = x - x_0$ and $\beta = y - y_0$ and the equations of the motion become

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{\alpha} - 2n\dot{\beta} &= \Omega_x(x_0 + \alpha, y_0 + \beta) = \alpha \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} + \beta \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy}, \\ \ddot{\beta} + 2n\dot{\alpha} &= \Omega_y(x_0 + \alpha, y_0 + \beta) = \alpha \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yx} + \beta \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy}. \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

where ‘o’ indicates that the partial derivatives are to be calculated at the libration points under consideration.

The characteristic equation of the Equations (26) is given by

$$\lambda^4 + (4n^2 - \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} - \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy})\lambda^2 + \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx}\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy} - (\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy})^2 = 0, \tag{27}$$

which is a fourth degree equation in λ .

Let $\lambda^2 = \Lambda$, therefore the characteristic Equation (27) becomes

$$\Lambda^2 + (4n^2 - \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} - \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy})\Lambda + \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx}\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy} - (\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy})^2 = 0 \tag{28}$$

which is a quadratic equation in Λ . If Λ_1 and Λ_2 are the roots of the Equation (28) then

$$\Lambda_{1,2} = \frac{-p \pm \sqrt{p^2 - 4q}}{2}, \tag{29}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} p &= 4n^2 - \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} - \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy}, \\ q &= \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx}\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy} - (\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy})^2. \end{aligned}$$

and the roots of the characteristic Equation (27) are given by

$$\lambda_{1,2} = \pm\sqrt{\Lambda_1} \text{ and } \lambda_{3,4} = \pm\sqrt{\Lambda_2}. \tag{30}$$

The libration point (x_0, y_0) is said to be stable if $\Lambda_1 < 0$ and $\Lambda_2 < 0$.

Case I: At the non-collinear libration point L_4 , $r_2 = 1$, $x = \mu - 1 + \cos\psi$, $y = \sin\psi$ and $r_1 = 2 \sin(\psi/2)$.

Therefore, Ω_{xx} , Ω_{yy} and Ω_{xy} at L_4 are given by:

$$\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} = 1 - \mu + 3\mu \cos^2 \psi - \frac{(1-\mu)}{8} \csc^3 \frac{\psi}{2} - \frac{3(1-\mu)}{32} (1 - \cos \psi)^2 \csc^5 \frac{\psi}{2} + \frac{3}{10} (1 - \mu + 5\mu \cos^2 \psi) A,$$

$$\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy} = \frac{1}{32} \left(32 - 32\mu - 4 \csc^3 \frac{\psi}{2} + 4\mu \csc^3 \frac{\psi}{2} + 96\mu \sin^2 \psi + 3 \csc^5 \frac{\psi}{2} \sin^2 \psi - 3\mu \csc^5 \frac{\psi}{2} \sin^2 \psi \right) \\ \frac{3}{10} (1 - \mu + 5\mu \sin^2 \psi) A,$$

$$\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy} = 3\mu \cos \psi \sin \psi - \frac{3(1-\mu)}{32} (1 - \cos \psi) \csc^5 \frac{\psi}{2} \sin \psi + \frac{3}{2} \mu \cos \psi \sin \psi A.$$

Fig. 4: Stability region for $r_2 = 1, A = 10^{-3}$

As shown in the Fig. 4, at the black spot both Λ_1 and Λ_2 are negative it means the non-collinear libration point are stable in $57^\circ \leq \psi \leq 60^\circ$ and $0.0899... \leq \mu \leq 0.06148...$. In the interval $(0^\circ, 57^\circ)$, Λ_1 is positive and Λ_2 is negative for $\mu \in [0, \frac{1}{2}]$. Thus, the non-collinear libration points exist in the interval $(0^\circ, 57^\circ)$ are unstable. The non-collinear libration points exist in the interval $[57^\circ, 60^\circ]$ are stable for different critical values of mass parameter μ_c . In the interval $(60^\circ, 180^\circ)$, Λ_1 and Λ_2 are complex roots which shows that the non-collinear libration points are unstable in the interval $(60^\circ, 180^\circ)$, $0 \leq \mu \leq \frac{1}{2}$.

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Since, the non-collinear libration points lying in the lower-half of unit circle are just the mirror image of the points lying in upper-half. So, if the points in upper-half are stable then their corresponding points in lower-half will also be stable and vice-versa.

Case II: At the non-collinear libration point L_4 , $r_1 = p$, $r_2 = \sqrt{1 + 2p \cos \varphi + p^2}$, $x = \mu + p \cos \varphi$, $y = p \sin \varphi$. Therefore, Ω_{xx} , Ω_{yy} and Ω_{xy} at L_4 are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} &= \mu + 3(1 - \mu) \cos^2 \varphi + \frac{3\mu(1 + 2 \cos \varphi + \cos^2 \varphi)}{(2 + 2 \cos \varphi)^{5/2}} - \frac{\mu}{(2 + 2 \cos \varphi)^{3/2}} + \left[\frac{-3}{10} + \frac{3\mu}{5} + \frac{9}{5}(1 - \mu) \cos^2 \varphi \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{3\mu(3 + 8 \cos \varphi + 7 \cos^2 \varphi + 2 \cos^3 \varphi)}{2(2 + 2 \cos \varphi)^{7/2}} - \frac{3\mu(3 + 6 \cos \varphi + 4 \cos^2 \varphi)}{10(2 + 2 \cos \varphi)^{5/2}} \right] A, \\ \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy} &= 3(1 - \mu) \cos \varphi \sin \varphi + \frac{3\mu \sin \varphi (1 + \cos \varphi)}{(2 + 2 \cos \varphi)^{5/2}} + \left[\frac{9}{5}(1 - \mu) \cos \varphi \sin \varphi + \frac{3\mu \sin \varphi (1 + 5 \cos \varphi + 2 \cos^2 \varphi)}{2(2 + 2 \cos \varphi)^{7/2}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{3\mu \sin \varphi (1 + 2 \cos \varphi)}{5(2 + 2 \cos \varphi)^{5/2}} \right] A, \\ \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy} &= \mu - \frac{\mu}{(2 + 2 \cos \varphi)^{3/2}} + 3(1 - \mu) \sin^2 \varphi + \frac{3\mu \sin^2 \varphi}{(2 + 2 \cos \varphi)^{5/2}} + \left[\frac{-3}{10} + \frac{3\mu}{5} - \frac{3\mu(3 + 2 \cos \varphi)}{10(2 + 2 \cos \varphi)^{5/2}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{9(1 - \mu) \sin^2 \varphi}{5} + \frac{3\mu \sin^2 \varphi (3 + 2 \cos \varphi)}{2(2 + 2 \cos \varphi)^{7/2}} - \frac{6\mu \sin^2 \varphi}{5(2 + 2 \cos \varphi)^{5/2}} \right] A. \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 5: Stability region for $r_1 = p$ and $A = 10^{-3}$

From the Fig. 5, at the dark shaded-region Λ_1 and Λ_2 both are negative *i.e.* the non-collinear libration points are stable in $0^\circ \leq \varphi \leq 140^\circ$ and $0 \leq \mu_c \leq 0.127284\dots$. This is also observed from the Fig. 5, as φ increases the interval of critical value of mass parameter decreases. When $\varphi = 0^\circ$, the libration point L_4 is stable for the critical value of mass parameter $\mu_c \leq 0.127284\dots$ but this is a collinear libration point. Hence we have a collinear Libration point which is stable for $\mu_c \leq 0.127284\dots$.

6. Conclusion:

In the present paper, we have considered the smaller primary as an oblate spheroid with axes a, b, c such that $a = b > c$ and the bigger one a point mass in the circular restricted three-body problem. The non-collinear libration points are obtained in three ways out of which first two ways are unique and never included in the previous studies and the third one is a well known solution used by many mathematicians.

In case I, we eliminated r_1 from the Equations (19) and (20) and supposed that $r_2 = 1$ *i.e.* the non-collinear libration points are lying on the circumference of a unit circle centered at m_2 . The non-collinear libration points depend upon ψ , where ψ is the angle between the infinitesimal mass m_3, m_2 and m_1 lying in the same plane (Fig. 2). We have also studied the stability of the libration points in linear sense and found that the non-collinear libration points exist in the interval $[57^\circ, 60^\circ]$ are stable for different critical values of mass parameter μ_c while the non-collinear libration points exist in the interval $(60^\circ, 180^\circ)$ are unstable for $0 \leq \mu \leq \frac{1}{2}$.

In case II, we eliminated r_2 from the Equations (19) and (20) and found that the non-collinear libration points are lying on the circumference of a circle of radius p centered at m_1 . We supposed that angle $(Pm_1m_3) = \varphi, 0^\circ \leq \varphi \leq 360^\circ$ (Fig. 3), therefore the location of the non-collinear libration point $L_4(x, y)$ is given by $x = \mu + p \cos\varphi, y = p \sin\varphi$ (Equation-23). The non-collinear libration point L_4 is stable in $0^\circ \leq \varphi \leq 140^\circ$ for different critical value of mass parameter μ_c and it is unstable in $140^\circ < \varphi < 180^\circ$. For $\varphi = 0^\circ$, a **collinear libration point** is found and this point is **stable** for the critical value of mass parameter $\mu_c \leq 0.127284\dots$.

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